

She's Lost Control Again: The Next Generation Of Copyright Challenges Over Next-Generation Interactive Music

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Abstract

Music production has entered a new era. Songs can be generated with limited human direction at a rate faster than it takes to listen to them. Fluid musical works can generate indefinitely, where the model itself may be more akin to the composition. As levels of speed and control of GenAI tools increase, the ability to instantly transform music at user direction with a high degree of control may soon be upon us, such that listeners can personalise what they are listening to. This would render music interactive, each song its own instrument to be played, each audience an instant artist inasmuch as they are able to direct the songs they listen to towards the sound they are interested in. As the advent of recorded music irreversibly changed musical production, this may be the next watershed moment. The moment where media becomes amorphous and fluid, everything able to be turned into everything else. How exactly is copyright supposed to make sense of this? The simple answer is – it (for the most part) prohibits it. As we enter an era where copyright is inherently at odds with a new form of creative production built on instant transformation of existing content, it may drive that production towards the only platforms that can legally support it. Yet, the more powerful these platforms are, the harder it is for rightsholders to set the terms around which their work is enjoyed within these platforms. The worse these terms are for rightsholders, the less value that rightsholders can extract from within the platform directly, placing greater value on attribution for the work such that it can lead to a separate stream of profit elsewhere (such as through selling tickets to shows). However, if works can be easily regenerated into similar works without attribution on the platforms, copyright may incentivise public domain regeneration, and in turn place even greater pressure on rightsholders to license their works out to these platforms. This means that if instant creative reproduction becomes widely accessible, rather than protecting musicians, copyright may embolden a market dynamic that undermines its own value and power for musicians in contemporary digital creative economies.

1 Introduction – The Current State of Affairs

Music production has entered a new era. Songs can be generated with limited human direction at a rate faster than it takes to listen to them (Cooper, 2025). Fluid musical works can generate indefinitely, where the model itself may be more akin to the composition. Copyright has been decidedly confused when dealing with this new generation of AI-generated music. The traditional economic rationale for copyright is to incentivise innovative production, positing that no rational market participant would invest in the creation of work if they were not then granted exclusive rights to that work (Hurt & Schuchman, 1966; Ohly & Klippel, 2007; Klass et al., 2021; Drahos & Braithwaite, 2002).¹ Now, staggering amounts of work can be produced with negligible investment,

¹ This is enshrined in the US Constitution, Article I, Section 8, Clause 8. European copyright legislation, despite its greater foundations in *droits d'auteurs*, still primarily justifies itself in its Recitals as on the basis of stimulating a single European market. *See for example*: Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society, *OJL 167* Recitals 1-4.

challenging the foundations of this rationale. Indeed, innovative new forms of works are becoming progressively easier to create with decreasing technological barriers to entry for artists.

Why, then, if copyright seeks to stimulate innovation and production, have the majority of copyright frameworks worldwide sought to deny copyright to AI-generated works, given they can be both innovative *and* developed at a massive scale (Cooper, 2025)? For the most part, it has been under the auspices that copyright is for *human* authors, yet this rationale has only been brandished against human authors so far. Where this policy gets into the most trouble is in ascertaining exactly which works count as AI-generated (and therefore don't receive copyright) and which works are sufficiently "human-authored" (in which case, they do). To complicate matters further, this man vs machine copyright delineation is applied in many frameworks *for each element*, such that the AI-generated verse would *not* receive copyright but the "human-composed" chorus would (eg United States Copyright Office, 2025).

This is especially tricky, given the infinite spectrum of AI uses that can be applied in the creation of a musical work. Some of these don't impact copyrightability at all (say, those used for effects or voice cloning) (Sorokin, 2022; Lund, 2013; Rahmatian, 2014). Those that do affect copyrightable elements can be relied on to entirely different levels, from those that effect the final work negligibly to those that create entire works with negligible effort (Cooper, 2025). Even generative models that run endlessly spewing out infinite streams of music may have been meticulously designed by a musician to create something artistically distinct deeply in line with their own authorial vision. The tools themselves are also constantly changing, as are our relationships with them, such that any qualitative assessments of our ability to predict outputs or to adjudicate requisite levels of authorial expression for each and every use of a tool present in the creative process appears decidedly tangled for any unlucky judge tasked with doing so (Cooper, Lehr & Stocker, 2024).

Worse, the thresholds for making any such assessment are not clearly set *anywhere*, let alone internationally harmonised (Cooper, Lehr & Stocker, 2024). In turn, even were one privy to the entire creative process of any individual song such that we could see exactly where, how and to what extent every single AI tool was used in its process, it may still be unclear which elements were overly reliant on AI tools and which were not in most national frameworks. Instead, each national framework exists on "the same spectrum of uncertainty - an infinite quagmire of potential use cases to be assessed on a case-by-case basis in each country individually", with partially AI-generated works more likely to receive copyright in China, less likely in the USA, and not entirely certain in either (Cooper, 2025). Thus, as it stands, artists utilising AI in varied ways while creating music are for the most part left unsure which elements of their music hold copyright in which jurisdictions.

Still, even if these thresholds were clear, we would be unable to evaluate any work against them without a complete understanding of their entire creative process, such that we knew exactly how AI was used at every step of the way in order to ascertain which elements of the work receive copyright and which do not. Currently, national frameworks are reliant on AI disclosure from artists. Yet, one may question why exactly an artist would go to the effort of keeping a record of every single time they used an AI tool in their process, increasingly mere buttons in creative workstations, when they have never had to do this for any other digital tools and it is entirely in service of them losing rights to their work.

Without a means of differentiating when material is developed with GenAI, without GenAI, initially with GenAI but then partly modified without GenAI, or initially without GenAI but then partly modified with GenAI, separating out the copyrightability of every element is unworkable and will surely lead to authors registering copyright in the entirety of their work if it cannot be proven otherwise.

Although these difficulties have led to widespread interest in technological solutions, such as watermarking tools, to help regulate AI-generated creativity, none of the current solutions are reliable in determining whether GenAI has been used at all, let alone at a granular enough level for an element-by-element qualitative analysis of a work's creative process (European Union Intellectual Property Office, 2020; Heikillä, 2024; Alkhafaji et al., 2020; Begum & Uddin, 2020; Jacob & Mitra, 2015; Chen et al., 2023; Sadasivan, 2023; Srinivasan, 2024; Gregory & Llorente, 2023). In summary, then, while national copyright frameworks worldwide have been quick to assert that AI-generated works should *not* receive copyright, they have done so without a clear means of

assessing what counts as AI-generated and what does not, nor with any robust means to audit how people have created their works against this still uncertain standard.

Although this policy of denying copyright to GenAI musical works will be difficult to enforce in the present, it may have more unintended impacts on the near-future-state of GenAI-assisted creativity, which is bound to substantially shift the means by which we produce, consume and disseminate music. Critically, as levels of speed and control of GenAI tools increase, so does the capacity for interactivity with musical works, blurring the line between artist and audience. In this short paper, I will roadmap potential consequences of current-state copyright policy on near-future-state GenAI-enabled works, which may drive new forms of musical production towards massive prosumer platforms that are able to provide spaces where audiences can legally transform works. However, the more that music is driven towards these platforms, the less valuable copyright over musical works may be. In turn, copyright is at risk of losing value to musical rightsholders as a means of generating revenue for musicians.

2 Copyright & Emergent Gen-AI Enabled Interactive Music

Right now, consumer-facing text-to-music generators, such as Udio and Suno, allow users to upload pieces of music to be instantly remixed and repurposed, granting the ability to change lyrics and styles based on consumer direction (Dredge, 2024). Similarity meters allow users to choose how similar they want regenerated works to resemble those which they have uploaded. Musical inpainting allows for users to target certain areas of songs and regenerate them as directed.

As levels of speed and control of GenAI tools increase, the ability to instantly transform music at user direction with a high degree of control may soon be upon us, such that listeners can personalise what they are listening to – “change the female vocal to a male vocal and make the bassline funkier and throw in a dubstep beat underneath it, please”. This would render music interactive, each song its own instrument to be played, each audience an instant artist inasmuch as they are able to direct the songs they listen to towards the sound they are interested in.

Lowered technical skill thresholds to create music coincide with a time where the line between amateur and professional content production has also blurred. Social media platforms like TikTok host music which is both social and artistic. New tools render even the most basic of video or song ideas easily transformed and elevated into something aesthetically stimulating. Seconds-long musical fragments go viral, reaching far greater audiences than most professional musicians can ever dream of. All content uploaded holds the lottery potential to explode across the platform, turning something made quickly for fun into something massively lucrative.

As the advent of recorded music irreversibly changed musical production, this may be the next watershed moment. The moment where media becomes amorphous and fluid, everything able to be turned into everything else. How exactly is copyright supposed to make sense of this?

The simple answer is – it (for the most part) prohibits it. Without the rights to the masters recordings nor their underlying compositions, listeners generally have no right to transform or rework the music that they listen to if the resultant output contains protected material from the input (eg. Pelham, 2019; Lessig, 2008; Li, 2018). Although listeners are allowed to *privately* transform music *that they own*, they would not be able to share their transformations. Critically, many listeners do not own most the music that they listen to, primarily reliant instead on subscriptions to music streaming services. Last year, 91.3% of “album-equivalent consumption” in the US was through streaming services (Luminate, 2025). Thus, there is an instant tension between copyright and these new forms of interactive music. Namely, this new means of interacting with music would be, for the most part, illegal, unless huge amounts of musical rights can be cleared to enable users to do so.

Naturally, individual listeners are broadly unlikely and unable to clear all of these rights to the music that they wish to transform. Large consumer streaming services that license their music from distributors also do not have the relevant rights for users to be able to transform and remix the music that they listen to. In turn, the natural benefactors of instantly remixable music interaction are large prosumer social media platforms, such as TikTok, that can benefit from their massive network effects, holding widespread licenses for their large user bases to transform any content that is native to their platform.

Of course, these social media platforms also do not have the rights for users to transform and remix music that is distributed off-platform and has been licensed to the platform, as is the case with most label-distributed music. Inherently, then, any content containing music where the rights required to remix it have not been cleared may be at a disadvantage to platform-native music, which users can have free rein over to use new transformative creative tools.

This may have an interesting impact on the dynamic between label-distributed music and platform-native music. Traditionally, the latter is not appreciated as legitimate an artistic work as the former. It is possible that this will be exacerbated if the platform-native music becomes malleable and shape-shifting while other music remains static, to be consumed as their creator designed them. Yet, to the extent that platform-native music is more coherent with memetic platform architectures and in turn can more readily go viral and proliferate, rightsholders may feel pressured to allow users to transform their works within the walls of the platforms fearing that otherwise, their works will not compete as well within recommender algorithmic infrastructures.

This may be especially true given the grim current-state of revenue opportunities for musicians. Commodity value of music is now dwarfed by other revenue streams with physical music revenue in global decline, often marketed now as a form of specialist merch (IFPI, 2025; Peoples, 2024; Luminare, 2025). Rather, many musicians are largely reliant on the often meagre payouts from streaming royalties and money made playing live shows. (Composer Jennifer Walshe has written that her friend's daughter streams Taylor Swift on mute when she listens to her Taylor Swift vinyl to ensure that it counts towards her Spotify Wrapped, suggesting that untracked physical listening almost holds an unofficial quality to a certain listener (2024).)

A study last year found that a massive 70% of European musicians were not satisfied with streaming royalties (Tencer, 2024). Spotify themselves estimated in 2023 that they only hosted 225,000 professional musicians worldwide (compared with an estimated 11.6 million full-time "content creators" in the US alone) with only "more than 30%" of them (namely, 67,500 worldwide) making more than \$10,000 a year from Spotify royalties (Loud and Clear by Spotify, 2023; Keller, Evans and Schneider, 2023; Poliks, 2024). Thus, an artist would require an estimated 10 million streams at 0.003 cents per stream with a 50/50 label split in order to reach the US federal minimum wage. Despite this, the vast majority of professional recording musicians continue to license their music out to streaming services. Without any viable market for the music elsewhere, musicians feel that they must try to build visibility on streaming services. If they are able to do so, they can then hope to monetise their fame elsewhere, such as through live performances. Naturally, the musician famous enough to have 10 million streams will hope to convert that level of fame to an avenue more lucrative than the minimum wage they are receiving from the streams themselves.

Yet, to the extent that a piece of music is primarily valuable to a musician as a means of advertising some secondary stream of value, rather than directly in and of itself, the value of the copyright over that piece of music is itself vastly diminished. Of course, attribution remains critical. Yet copyright may even be detrimental to that secondary value stream. Copyright allows rightsholders to control uses of their work. If the revenue for the work is to be gained through its wide proliferation, then the less restricted the flow of the work across platforms, the better. The work *needs* to be *widely* copied. Thus, copyright is of inherently less value to the extent that value is derived from a work in its *uncontrollability*, such that users are free to redistribute the work widely. Even works where the rightsholder has granted permission for them to be shared may theoretically suffer to the extent that there is uncertainty around whether it is permitted to share the work or not. Thus, even the spectre of copyright may have a deleterious effect on a work's prospective virality.

Control over a work is also of diminishing value to the extent that any commercial decisions for dissemination of the work are predetermined. As streaming services now dominate as the primary space by which listeners consume music, musical rightsholders are increasingly limited in their options as to where they wish to distribute their music (Luminare, 2025). Although different musical distributors offer different terms to musicians, royalties are largely governed by the terms set by the streaming platforms with many distributors profiting through charging upfront fees (Herstand, 2025). To the extent that any musical rightsholder can somehow recreate past artist / listener dynamics wherein withholding access to their music would allow them to set the terms by which interested listeners could get access to that music, then their copyright remains analogously valuable.

Instead, withholding music from streaming platforms is generally considered a form of engagement self-destruction, massively reducing exposure to music in an attention economy dominated by streaming platforms (Luminate, 2025).

Thus, the control granted to musical rightsholders over music can in practice feel like a right “to choose” to agree to the unfavourable terms set by streaming platforms, unless they can find a better revenue stream from the music elsewhere or unless they are in the rare position that they have enough negotiating power to renegotiate those terms. Inherently then, musical copyright is of decreasing value the less that any other viable market exists for musical works outside of platform architectures, with their own predetermined terms.

These are two critical factors to appreciate when considering potential pressure to grant licences to remix music on platforms in an age of GenAI-enabled musical interactivity:

- 1) the more power platforms hold as the primary space for music consumption, the less valuable the copyright is in the music.
- 2) The more that value is derived from a work’s *uncontrollability*, the less valuable the copyright in that work.

Thus, while traditionally, rightsholders may be reluctant to grant widespread licences for users to transform their works, the pressure to do so may be exacerbated if their works are primarily profitable in their memetic spread across platforms, generating attention to be monetised elsewhere. Indeed, many of the most famous musical phenomena of recent years have been directly linked to viral platform phenomena. Emblematically, “Brat Summer”, the viral social phenomenon that accompanied the release of Charli XCX’s album “Brat” last year, could not have proliferated across social media platforms if those platforms did not have the rights for users to share videos with “Brat” soundtracks (Maguire, 2024). The memetic focus of social media prosumer platforms such as TikTok is visible in their royalty payout scheme, which pays per video that uses the song, rather than per stream of that video. Yet, these royalties are notoriously low, generally significantly less valuable even than streaming service royalties (McIntyre, 2024).

As mentioned earlier, social media platforms do not generally have rights for users to transform or remix music licensed to their platforms. Still, during the “Brat Summer” phenomenon, social media platforms were replete with remixed, reversioned, and repurposed riffs on Charli XCX’s album. Many of these were allowed to spread across the platform, despite their clear illegality. Why would anyone want to take them down? You simply can’t pay for advertising like that.

Indeed, TikTok’s power in the music industry was on full display during last year’s negotiation breakdown between TikTok and Universal Music Group (UMG), wherein UMG pulled their entire catalogue from TikTok leaving all content previously soundtracked by UMG music silent (Chmielewski and Shepardson, 2024). Immediately, artists on UMG started seeking workarounds to have their music put back on TikTok. Some music that was not signed to UMG, yet was partly credited to UMG songwriters, removed these songwriters from the metadata in order for the music to stay available on TikTok (Money 4 Nothing, 2024). Olivia Rodrigo, one of UMG’s most lucrative artists, was unable to promote her new album with official versions of her music on TikTok, and instead shared content that included illegally uploaded sped-up versions of her songs that was able to dodge TikTok’s automated Content ID filters (Money 4 Nothing, 2024). Taylor Swift, who despite being a UMG artist has her own specific contract wherein she retains ownership of her own recordings and songwriting rights, cut her own licensing deal with TikTok to get her music back on there (Chmielewski and Shepardson, 2024). It was reported that Swift’s deal significantly weakened UMG’s position and in turn was a major factor in breaking the stalemate (Sisario, 2024; Chmielewski and Shepardson, 2024; Money 4 Nothing, 2024). Although both parties ultimately claimed to be satisfied with the confidential terms landed upon, the deal was widely considered within the music industry as a great win for TikTok and a clear expression of its power (Sisario, 2024; Money 4 Nothing, 2024). At the end of the day, it was more important to maintain TikTok visibility to promote non-TikTok revenue streams than it was to try to derive far greater value from TikTok itself.

Given these market circumstances, if user transformation and regeneration of content ends up being especially popular, traditional consumptive listening may find itself in competition for listener’s

attention with more interactive modes of listening and reproduction, which would have both the potential to be immediately republished as well as potentially gamified to try to lock in listener engagement. Of course, this is speculative. It remains to be seen to what extent listeners are interested in bespoke musical content, as well as to the extent that we will be interested in transforming music for our own private enjoyment versus doing so for creative or social production. Still, there is clear cause for discomfort when we consolidate this legal and economic context in which Gen-AI enabled musical reproduction emerges.

To review: it will be difficult to legally enable transformation of music without either the large network effects of huge user bases or the power to negotiate large amounts of licenses. The easiest benefactors thus appear to be large platforms that will be able to automatically clear rights *en masse* for native content as part of their terms of services.

Yet, the value of copyright is diminished to the extent that large platforms are powerful enough to dominate as the primary space by which music is consumed, as rightsholders are therefore beholden to the market terms set by these platforms. Thus, copyright may drive this new form of media interactivity into the hands of the players whose power would undermine its own value. This is exacerbated to the extent that value in the music comes through its uncontrollability, which would seemingly be the case for interactive media within social media platform architectures.

Thus, copyright in musical works may wind up broadly subservient to alternative algorithmic proprietary rights and terms. If rightsholders rely on platforms to drive promotion for the music off the platforms, yet those platforms are themselves the only spaces where new interactive forms of production and consumption are allowed, pressure to allow transformation of works on those platforms may be significant.

If this pressure mounts, such that platforms are able to license the transformation of large amounts of label-distributed music to sit alongside the music natively uploaded to the platforms, we might consider this a watershed moment in copyright history – wherein norms have been flipped such that users now have legal permission to infinitely remix a significant amount of copyrighted music, albeit locked within the walled gardens of platforms to do so. (The terms by which royalties would be paid out in such instances is an open question).

We may then find that interactive and remixable media takes place on certain prosumer social media platforms, hoping to generate interest for music which is primarily enjoyed in its official or static version elsewhere on consumer streaming platforms. Still, to the extent that interactive music is itself popular and that revenue is attached to name value of the artist, rather than the individual work itself, it is likely that musicians will try to create music inherently to be repurposed in and of itself, rather than as an ad for an official version elsewhere. In turn, music might be composed inherently to serve as memetic a function as possible, with the most popular versions those that are the most inviting for individual users to put their own spin on them. It is clear in such circumstances that copyright may fast lose relevance as a driver of value, while *attribution* will become absolutely paramount. It is in this context that denying copyright to Generative AI works has unintended consequences.

3 Denying Copyright to GenAI Works & The Public Domain Metamorphosis

Critically, the analysis so far assumes that large social media platforms have access to competitive GenAI models to enable an acceptable enough quality of on-platform transformation. If platforms are unable to integrate the best quality GenAI tools or if they are overly limited in the content that users are able to transform on-platform, then listeners that wish to transform content will be reliant on off-platform tools to create remixes without legal permission. Currently, this is easily achieved. The consumer-facing landscape for GenAI text-to-music tools is led by Udio, Suno and Stable Audio (O'Donnell, 2025; Stability AI, 2024). Stable Audio relegated itself to legally licensed music to train its model, while Udio and Suno are reliant on the questionable legality of training models on unlicensed copyrighted materials without permission (and are currently fighting this position out in court) (UMG Recordings, Inc. v. Suno, Inc., 2024; UMG Recordings, Inc. v. Uncharted Labs, Inc., 2024).

When uploading audio to Udio and Suno to transform, users tick a box where they assert that they are not uploading protected content that they do not have the rights to. They are then able to immediately create remixes of the uploaded content, even if it is protected. Although the tools appear to have some light Content ID mechanisms that will reject some requests for especially large artists, in my own research, this is the rare exception rather than the rule, with the overwhelming majority of protected content being easily transformed immediately.

Critically, in many jurisdictions such as the USA and the UK, Content ID filters are not mandated (17 U.S.C. § 512, 1998; Electronic Commerce (EC Directive) Regulations 2002, SI 2002/2013, reg. 19 (UK)). Safe harbor provisions, such as those in the US' Digital Millennium Copyright Act's (DMCA), only require platforms to remove copyrighted content after receiving notice from the rightsholder. While Article 17 of the European Union's Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market (DSM) does establish that Online Content Sharing Service Providers (OCSSPs) must make "best efforts to ensure the unavailability" of copyrighted works (widely interpreted as referring to filters and automated content recognition systems), the denial of copyright to generated works may partly provide a loophole here, as a platform is only considered an OCSSP if one of its main purposes is to "store and give the public access to a large amount of copyright-protected works" (Cooper, 2025; Keller, 2020; DSM Directive, 2019). Although works shared on the platforms would contain copyrighted material to the extent that outputs resemble their protected inputs, the platforms may argue that their intention is to give access primarily to *public access* GenAI works.

To the extent that such an argument may be considered tenuous if the AI models continue to maintain public platforms wherein users can listen to user-generated music (including those protected inputs that have survived in their regenerated outputs), it highlights the broader tension in denying copyright to AI-generated outputs – namely, that it incentivises privately regenerating the protected materials into something similar, yet not the same, in order to be able to legally interact with or transform the newly public-domain music. Each time a piece of music is regenerated, it may contain some protected element from the input – forming a copyright-protected core surrounded by unprotected generative runoff (United States Copyright Office, 2025). Once the protected core has been entirely regenerated into something else, a kind of public domain metamorphosis has been completed, and listeners can now freely upload, interact with and transform the resulting piece of music.

This means that work is only protected inasmuch as some element of the original is considered necessary in a generated output. If maintaining the attributes of the original is preferred but something similar would suffice, then creators may generate out the protected elements into public domain knock-offs in order to be able to have complete rights to transform or interact with the resulting work. Thus, the dubstep knock-off of a Taylor Swift song which is only interesting inasmuch as it contains the popular Taylor Swift element will remain protected. Yet, if someone wants to remix a less well-known underground artist, their copyright may stand in the way of their attribution if it is easier to simply generate out the protected attributes of their work into similar nonprotected attributes than it is to seek this artist's permission to do so.

Thus, musical artists with strong senses of persona (and whose regenerated works are more likely to form around specific elements within their music, such as specific catchy choruses or their own persona) are better protected than artists without a clear persona (or whose personas are most evident in attributes that are *not* copyrightable, such as their specific sound or style). Thus, copyright inherently supports the aforementioned meme-music in its offer of protection – as artists who do not compose specific elements that would be desired in regenerated outputs may have their work replaced with regenerated public-access stand-in elements. Thus, artists who are not as reliant on attribution due to their fame are well-protected. Yet, those who would benefit most from attribution may be in the unenviable position of either granting open licenses to their content to be transformed on prosumer platforms, or risk having easily generated knock-offs based on their work proliferate instead. Copyright may thus, counter-purposively, incentivise regeneration without attribution.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, I have sought to roadmap some of the potential unintended and undesired consequences of current copyright regimes when applied to emergent forms of GenAI-enabled music production

and consumption in relation to contemporary digital music economies, which are widely dependent on both consumptive streaming and prosumptive social media platform infrastructures.

Copyright is ostensibly supposed to incentivise innovative production while rewarding authors for their creative contributions. As we enter an era where copyright is inherently at odds with a new form of creative production built on instant transformation of existing content, it may drive that production towards the platforms that can legally support it. Yet, the more powerful these platforms are, the harder it is for rightsholders to set the terms around which their work is enjoyed within these platforms.

The worse these terms are for rightsholders, the less value that rightsholders can extract from within the platform directly, placing greater value on attribution for the work such that it can lead to a separate stream of profit elsewhere (such as through selling tickets to shows). However, if works can be easily regenerated into similar works without attribution on the platforms, copyright may incentivise public domain regeneration, and in turn place even greater pressure on rightsholders to license their works out to these platforms.

This means that if instant creative reproduction becomes widely accessible, rather than protecting musicians, copyright may embolden a market dynamic that undermines its own value and power for musicians in contemporary digital creative economies. Thus, contemporary debates around whether AI-generated works deserve the same protections as non-AI-generated works should not be based upon siloed legal theory alone but rather consider the likely near-state impacts of copyright policy on what is shaping up to be a century of foundationally different creative consumption, production and dissemination from those that came before.

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